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DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION & EDUCATION PLAN

SOLAR ENERGY FOR A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

Solar Energy for a Circular Economy

Deliverable D3.1
Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan

WP3. Dissemination, Communication and Education

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, D3.1 Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan, is a deliverable of the **SUNRISE** Project, which is funded by the European Union's H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 816336. The Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan identifies the main dissemination and communication objectives of the project and the activities and tools that will be defined and implemented in the current action and in future endeavours according to the target audiences.

The plan includes an evaluation of the initial KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) and proposes changes and additions to be taken into account in the short and long-term. In addition, an evaluation annex (Annex 1) is attached to the current document, containing the evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities carried out during the first months of the action. This analysis serves as the basis to propose changes in the initial plan and KPIs and define the backbone of the future strategies for dissemination, communication and education.

In the first half of the action, the project has reached a large number of supporters and followers, especially within the scientific community, including academic and industrial sectors. The main dissemination and communication tools planned have been deployed with a strong commitment from the consortium partners. The current supporting community is very active, but reaching further the general public and policy makers remains as one of the challenges. The release of key deliverables of the action, the Vision document, the Scientific and Technological roadmap, a joint Manifesto with ENERGY-X, the Innovation plan and the Governance outline will be key for increasing awareness and support for Artificial Photosynthesis in a broader context. Promotional online campaigns and competitions, as well as the organisation of national stakeholder face-to-face meetings and supporting audiovisual materials (videos, infographics, slides, etc.) will be crucial to fulfil the conditions needed for the success of the dissemination and communication strategy, complying with three conditions: 1. Continuous operation of communication tools; 2. Up to date and adapted content to address the different target audiences; 3. Active engagement at European and member states level.

The recently announced merging with ENERGY-X is a great opportunity to reach a larger community that will involve changes in the dissemination and communication actions as a new image and brand position will be needed and future goals will have to be agreed.

The short-term objectives defined in this plan are based on the first-months analysis trying to give answer to the current challenges and including the remaining actions planned at the proposal stage. The long-term objectives are based on the initial plan to develop a European large-scale initiative and will need to be further reviewed and agreed with ENERGY-X, a final thorough analysis including multiple go/no-go decisions will need to be done at the end of the CSA.

Finally, this plan highlights the actions correlation with the main points of the DMP (Data Management Plan), which is another of the public deliverables of the action (D3.4. Data Management Plan).

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1. PURSUE OF THE DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EDUCATION PLAN

The SUNRISE Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan is one of the deliverables of the WP3: Dissemination, Communication and Education. This document will be updated by the end of the current project, in February 2020 in particular including the common communication plan agreed with the ENERGY-X CSA consortium as the two CSA projects, SUNRISE and ENERGY-X agreed in July 2019 to merge at the end of the two ongoing CSAs.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to provide a formal planning document for the actions that will be done to ensure effective dissemination and communication about the project and its outcomes, according to the target audiences and based on the initial plan and the analysis of on-going activities. The plan takes into account the current state of the project and the last changes affecting it. Looking for effectiveness and simplicity, the plan has been divided in short-term and long-term objectives and actions. The short-term plan provides objectives and a more detailed description of actions until the end of the current CSA project, indicating also the responsibilities of the partners and the key messages to be communicated. While the long-term plan gives a brief description of the main dissemination, communication and education goals of a large-scale research and innovation initiative, providing a backbone of appropriate actions to be further developed after the end of the current preparative project.

2. CURRENT STATUS OF THE CSA PROJECT

As part of the Dissemination, Communication and Education Plan, one of the main goals of the SUNRISE CSA is to create a growing SUNRISE community that can contribute to work towards the SUNRISE's goals. The dissemination and communication actions must serve to attract new interested stakeholders and keep a fluid communication and interaction with the already numerous supporters and followers, contributing to create a growing ecosystem around the initiative. The actions are addressed to four main target groups: (A) research community, (B) industry sector, (C) policymakers, and (D) advocacy groups including citizens and students as well as NGOs and associations dedicated to sustainable and renewable technologies and solar conversion applications. Several strategies and tools have been put in place in the first months of the action to effectively disseminate and communicate the progression and outcomes throughout the one-year CSA. A description and evaluation of these actions can be found in Annex 1.

The continuous evaluation and analysis of actions is key to increase support for the project by involving more stakeholders and consolidate the blueprint dissemination and communication plan. KPIs were set as measurement tools in the proposal stage and, during the first half of the project, website and social media data have been collected in order to know whether the target audiences are being reached or not, according to the different KPIs, *e.g.* number of website visits, number of newsletter subscriptions, number of social media followers, etc. The main tools utilised to collect these metrics are Google analytics for the SUNRISE website, and the different free-of-charge available tools of each social network: Twitter analytics, Facebook insights, YouTube analytics, LinkedIn analytics, and ResearchGate stats (see Annex 1 for the metrics).

These analyses have been compared with the initial KPIs set in the proposal stage, see table below:

Table 1. KPI analysis throughout the first 5 months of the project

Tool	KPI	Target	Current status*
Website	Number of website visits	>50,000 at the end of CSA	4,458 ^a
	Number of newsletter subscriptions	>100 at the end of CSA	355 ^b
	Number of blog contributions and questions in the discussion forum	>500 at the end of CSA	- ^c
Social/Professional networks	Number of followers	>5,000 at the end of CSA	1,450
	Interactions (shares, likes)	>5,000 at the end of CSA	4,940
Smartphone app	Number of downloads	>1,000 at the end of CSA	- ^d
Databases (SOLAR resources, infrastructures)	Number of visits	>5,000 at the end of CSA	- ^e
CSA Events (symposium, industry workshops and meetings, outreach activities, etc.)	Number of attendees and sectors	SUNRISE Symposium >150 Outreach activities >200 (in total) Industry roadshows >20 (in total)	SUNRISE meetings ~ 260 ^f Outreach activities ~ 145 ^g
Letters/statements of support	Number	>200 at the end of CSA	222
Press releases	Number	>25 at the end of CSA (incl. translations, in at least 10 different languages)	>25 ^h

*Data collected until 31 July 2019, see Annex 1 for more information.

^a Visits between May and July to the updated website; ^b External subscriptions, not including partner and supporters contacts. ^c The discussion forum has not been further promoted and is not considered as a key indicator at this stage, see explanation below; ^d The SUNRISE App is in a demo stage to be developed during the CSA project and is not available for public download; ^e These databases are not ready yet; ^f Estimated number of attendees to the two main SUNRISE events organised, see below; ^g Estimated number of attendees to SUNRISE stands in outreach events; ^h Press releases clippings, links and mentions in external media.

The KPIs and the analysis of the dissemination and communication actions (see Annex 1) gives us some interesting information to shape the future goals and activities.

In the first place, SUNRISE has achieved to bring together a large and engaged community. The number of organisations officially endorsing support to the initiative is even larger than expected (222 supporters by 31 July 2019) and they actively contribute to the SUNRISE events and actions. For instance, the “SUNRISE Community Building Event” that was organized before the launch of the CSA to present the initiative to the supporting entities, already counted with around 90 participants (Brussels, 15 November 2018). This support has also been seen in the so called “ramp-up meeting”, the SUNRISE Stakeholders Workshop that took place at month 4 of the CSA with around 170 participants, in connection with the European Sustainable Energy Week, bringing together also policy representatives and interested individuals (Brussels, 17 and 18 June

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2019). The growing community effect can also be seen in the large number of newsletter subscribers that account not only for partners and supporters contacts, but also for other interested stakeholders.

One of the actions key to enlarge the community is the large number of events (conferences, workshops, meetings) where the SUNRISE partners have introduced the initiative (see Table 3, Annex 1).

The deployment of a new website, social media tools, a SUNRISE video and an active communication campaign including different online activities, press releases and partners interviews in specialized and mass media is also crucial to create an open community and reach different audiences. Regarding the number of followers in social media, although the current numbers of followers are moderated, the number of interactions is large, showing a very active and engaged community behind. Finally, the action has participated in two large outreach events, having an stand in the “Big Challenge Science Festival” in Norway and the European Sustainable Energy Week (where participated also in one of the sessions) reaching a large number of attendees, especially young students, in line with the expected indicators.

Some deviations from the initial plan need to be taken into account in the current analysis and future planning. Although there is a blog section developed in the web and visitors have access to a contact e-mail address and can leave messages in the ‘support us’ section, not many interactions have been received through these channels in the first months of the project. Instead, social media networks have become the real interaction points with the SUNRISE community, therefore the previous idea of a discussion forum has not been further promoted. Regarding the SUNRISE App, its main goal is to develop a new tool to facilitate the open access to scientific publications. Before developing this new concept, it has been decided that a needed previous step for its development will be the collection of feedback and experience of a first group of users within the consortium partners. Therefore, the already available demo will be used among the partners for the rest of the CSA providing the basis for future improvement.

In addition, other KPIs will need to be considered in accordance with the new/modified objectives and actions. For instance, the official SUNRISE video has proven to be a very powerful communication tool and a new YouTube channel was open with already a large number of views. Release of new videos and translation of the official video to more languages are two of the actions that will be included in the short-term plan (see point 4.4) and that will need to be monitored. Moreover, other qualitative KPIs are also important to show the value of the current digital ecosystem of SUNRISE:

- **Posts’ engagement:** the most engaging posts both on Twitter and Facebook are those related to SUNRISE events and news, rather than the external news that are shared on a regular basis. *e.g.* in May, the 2 top tweets in terms of engagement were one on the SUNRISE consortium meeting in Bologna (Italy) with 136 engagements, and another one announcing the Twitter chat on air pollution and renewable energy with 83. This means that SUNRISE’s audience is interested in the SUNRISE’s updates and that our followers are committed to the initiative.
- **Number of newsletter’s opens:** the first public SUNRISE newsletter was submitted on July 2, 2019 to 585 subscribers and it obtained 34,7% opens. Different newsletter updates have been sent to different recipients, obtaining different opening numbers, up to 45%. The opens will be monitored to see recipients’ interest and try to deal with problems encountered, like spam issues.
- **Average website visit duration:** the average website visit duration between the months of May and July is of 5:05 minutes. Likewise, the number of pages per visit is between 4,65 and 5,72, which tells that users are interested in more than one single item when they visit the SUNRISE website.

3. SHORT-TERM OBJECTIVES

For the next 6 months, the main objective will be to keep growing SUNRISE supports and community to ensure the continuation of the action, once the CSA is finished. In addition, the merging with the ENERGY-X preparative action beyond the end of the current CSAs (February 2020), agreed in July 2019, into a larger initiative will also need to be considered in the future. The short-term dissemination, communication and education plan will be built towards the following specific objectives:

- ***Strengthen the SUNRISE support and community by adapting and increasing the dissemination and communication tools and actions:*** increase the dissemination and communication tools' exploitation aiming to reach a broader audience, providing relevant and adapted contents. The reinforcement of the internal coordination among the communication departments of the different partners will be also key to better spread the word about the initiative. For the next months, the different planned actions intend to reach high audiences, while their continuous analysis will consider qualitative aspects as well, in order to increase not only the number of followers and supporters, but also their engagement.
- ***Increase policy makers and citizens' involvement:*** a preliminary analysis of the supporters, followers and events attendees shows that the scientific public, mostly academic but also industrial, is the most represented. For the next months, effort will be concentrated on reaching policy actors and decision makers, both at European and MS level, and the general public. SUNRISE partners have participated in many dissemination events such as conferences, workshops and specialized meetings, and a good number of them are also planned for the next months. In addition, special emphasis should be put on reaching policy makers in the last months of the action, aiming to get political support, as well. National Stakeholder Meetings have proved to be a very important tool to organize the national support around the initiative and get access to local and national funding bodies and decision-makers and their organization in the following months will thus be of paramount importance. The release of key deliverables and documents, like the roadmap, will largely help to attract policy maker's interest. Therefore, a broad promotion campaign among partners and supporters will be planned, including the involvement of experts and market mavens to further uphold action's key messages among the required audiences. In addition, other actions, like participation in local outreach activities, appearances and interviews in local media, organization of online contests/live activities, etc. will further help to reach the lay public's attention and get new supports.
- ***Work towards an education and inclusive plan to reach the younger generations:*** analyse the actions carried out with a more educational character and study their planning in a future large-scale initiative, getting the support of specialized organisations (*i.e.* university associations, foundations) and opening it to the inclusion of social sciences and ethical and legal aspects.
- ***Start planning joint actions with ENERGY-X:*** following the announcement of the merging of the two initiatives during the “Energy-chemistry nexus: towards a European sustainable energy & catalysis research initiative” session of the EuropaCat Conference (Aachen, Germany, 18-23 August), a press release announcing the merging has been jointly made by the two preparatory actions. Other joint communication and dissemination actions will be planned during the course of the preparatory actions and beyond, and in particular a key joint manifesto-style document is planned, and a new name and new identity for the future initiative (temporarily called SUN-ERGY). The definition and accordance of future dissemination, communication and education main objectives and actions will be discussed in the coming months and included in the updated version of the current deliverable, to be released at M12.

4. SHORT-TERM DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EDUCATION TOOLS AND ACTIONS

4.1. Dissemination objectives and audiences

The main goal behind the dissemination actions is to disclose the progress and results of the project to other professionals, within the scientific, technological and policy fields. Actions to raise awareness about the initiative and raise support from different sectors will be continued, to promote project knowledge, while actions to announce new updates, attendance to conferences, workshops, etc. are used for the promotion of project outcomes.

The four main target audiences A-D can be further divided in the following dissemination groups:

- Consortium members
- Scientific community
- Industrial stakeholders
- Other related projects and platforms
- Local, Member States and European policy actors
- Associations, NGOs

4.2. Dissemination tools and actions

- **Publications:** the preparative action will release important publications such as the Vision document, the Scientific and Technological roadmap and a joint Manifesto with ENERGY-X. Appropriate dissemination of these publications using the website, social media tools, newsletters and presentations at conferences and workshops will be key to raise awareness around these important documents and get interested stakeholders feedback and endorsement. In addition, it is important that news of the project keep appearing in specialized media to reach awareness of the initiative. A news flash was published in the European Photochemistry Association Newsletter and the project has been mentioned in several specialized media (see point 2.1 Annex 1). Other publications like research*eu, C&EN, etc. will be targeted. Finally, the SUNRISE App demo will serve to share the partners last publications related to the project enhancing knowledge transference within the consortium and improving the system for future development.
- **Presentations at conferences/workshops/networks/exhibitions:** The presentation of SUNRISE and its goals at key dissemination events is of great importance to increase the visibility of the project. Dissemination material like a poster, template slides and leaflets are available for all partners in the intranet PLAZA site. Consortium partners have introduced the project in more than 20 relevant events including international conferences and meetings of related national and international platforms and associations (*i.e.* Solar Fuels Network (UK), FOTOFUEL (ES), see Table 3 Annex 1). To further promote the action, a young researchers' travel grant contest was organized to promote their participation in dissemination events and in collaboration with E-MRS the action has also sponsored a poster prize in the E-MRS Spring Meeting. Further participation in industrial relevant events and fairs will also be targeted.
- **Presentations at EU Events and Funding Agencies:** SUNRISE actively participated in the European Sustainable Energy Week, EUSEW. Its Stakeholder Workshop (17-18 June 2019) was

organised in connection with the event, being one of the actions within the Energy Days. In addition, SUNRISE participated in the EUSEW conference, on June 20, the initiative's coordinator Huub de Groot took part in the panel session 'Energy storage to boost EU decarbonisation and competitiveness,' together with representatives of the European research initiatives BATTERY 2030+ and ENERGY-X. SUNRISE also held a stand at the Networking Village. Participation to further EU related events will be targeted, as well as meetings with policy representatives, both at EU and national level.

- **SUNRISE Events:** two main community events have already been organized (SUNRISE Consortium meeting, November 2018 and SUNRISE Stakeholder meeting, June 2019). A final SUNRISE Symposium might also be organized towards the end of the action. Whenever possible, this final Symposium will be organized in connection with the other preparative actions, or at least with ENERGY-X. In addition, the project has organized two more consortium meetings (Kick-off meeting, March 2019 and SUNRISE Consortium meeting, May 2019) key for the management of the project, but that have also included dissemination and interactive actions, like a streamline session for supporters on PRDs (Priority Research Directions) in the Kick-off meeting and an open session to Italian supporters, including a presentation by Prof. John Mathews (Macquarie University, Australia) in the Consortium meeting held in May 2019. The next planned meeting (9-11 October 2019) also includes a coordinated event with the Mission Innovation initiative aiming to build synergies. The openness and interactive character of the consortium meetings will be kept in the next ones, including the final Symposium, where possible collaboration with specialized supporters *i.e.* EuChems, E-MRS, etc. might be of interest.

Finally, the organization of national SUNRISE Stakeholders meetings is key to organize the initiatives supports at national level, identify innovation hubs, get more visibility and reach local and national policy makers. Several such national events thus were organized in different member states and other ones are planned or will be organized in the following months, see the list below for the already organized/planned ones.

- United-Kingdom: UK Solar Fuels Network Meeting, 28 March and Mission Innovation action plan meeting, 25 March, Cambridge
- France: meeting of the GDR solar fuels, 13-15 May, Saclay.
- Italy: Bologna, 16 May 2019.
- Poland: Warsaw, 5-6 June 2019.
- Switzerland: Empa Zürich, 27 September 2019.
- France: Maison des Universités, Paris, 8 October 2019.
- The Netherlands: Eindhoven, Symposium "Solar to Products", 6 November 2019
- Finland: Turku, 9 December 2019.

4.3. Communication objectives and audiences

The main goal behind the communication and outreach actions is to promote the project itself and its outcomes to other professionals within the scientific and technological fields, as well as to the society at large. To do so, the Communication Plan will schedule different actions aiming to reach general audiences beyond the scientific and industrial communities. The plan includes actions to raise awareness of the project, project knowledge, actions to announce new updates, events, etc. and actions for stakeholder's involvement

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like activities online and offline to boost the followers and supporters' active participation and engagement in the project.

In addition to the communication tools, outreach activities will also be developed to increase public engagement. The major goal of the outreach activities will be to attract the younger generations to learn more about the project and communicate the advances on the use of alternative energy sources among future end-users.

The four main target audiences A-D can be further divided in the following communication and outreach groups:

Communication:

- Consortium members
- Scientific community
- Industrial stakeholders
- Other related projects and platforms
- Policy makers
- Associations, NGOs
- Students
- General public

The outreach actions are conceived as educational events, SUNRISE will define specific outreach activities addressed to the following communities:

- Primary and secondary school students
- General public
- Professionals from different disciplines/sectors

4.4. Communication tools and actions

- **Website and social & professional media tools:** the SUNRISE initiative has a public website since September 2018, firstly managed by Carina Faber (UCL) and that has been updated in the first months of the action by the WP3 lead, ICIQ. The website is accessible at www.sunriseaction.eu and www.sunriseaction.com and is the main dissemination and communication tool of the project containing all relevant information about the initiative goals, events and updates, addressed to all the target audiences. The website includes a direct link to the intranet PLAZA (managed by M2i) and a password-protected site for sharing working documents with partners and supporters.

The action also counts with profiles in social networks to promote the content of the project's webpage, related projects and relevant news concerning artificial photosynthesis. The project has a profile in each of the following platforms:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/sunriseaction/>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/sunriseaction>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sunriseaction>

- YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWBoKlQrVNn_cJsTSwGz0pA
- ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/SUNRISE-Solar-Energy-for-a-Circular-Economy-EU-H2020-CSA-Ref-816336>

These tools will be further developed and adapted to the target audiences in the following months, monitoring contents views and interactions (for more information about the website and tools see Annex 1 and the deliverable 3.2). These will be also key to develop interactive actions.

- **Newsletters:** Public newsletters serve to further facilitate quick access to all SUNRISE stakeholders about the major news and outcomes of the project. The first public newsletter was sent on 2 July. A new one will be submitted every three months to be distributed among the subscribers interested in the project (free subscription available on the webpage – homepage and ‘support us’ page). The newsletters will also be available on the webpage.
- **Videos & podcasts:** The SUNRISE official video was released by the middle of June. Due to its success (750 views on YouTube and 1,200 views on LinkedIn) and in an effort to further promote the project for a general audience, it will be also translated to other European languages, *e.g.* Spanish Italian, French (already available), German and Polish.

Moreover, five more videos will be released in the following months containing partners interviews about several topics related with the project.

The consortium members will be encouraged to produce audiovisual material to be freely distributed through the webpage and the SUNRISE YouTube channel. Other external videos related to the artificial photosynthesis will be posted on the project’s website to attract the lay public’s attention to the topic. Finally, partners’ interviews with external media are encouraged. Some podcasts are already available on the YouTube channel.

- **Promotional material & infographics:** document templates, a factsheet, roll-ups, etc. are available to all partners for the promotion of the project. In addition, a general leaflet with the main aims and ideas of the project is also available. Besides this one, some more flyers will be prepared: a facts and figures flyer, aligning SUNRISE objectives with the current targets of the IPCC and the UNDP; and 3 circular economy infographics.
- **Press releases & media clippings:** Three press releases have been distributed for mainstream media to announce the project start, to highlight the Stakeholders Workshop and to announce merging plans with ENERGY-X (see Annex 1 for more information). At least one more press release will be released at the end of the action to summarize the main achievements and inform about next steps. Interviews and reports on external media, especially on local media, will be encouraged in the following months to reach society at large.
- **Interactive actions:** the action has launched online events to celebrate International days, like an online interview with Hervé Bercegol, SUNRISE deputy coordinator, on the occasion of the International Day of Light, and a Twitter chat on occasion of the World Environment Day. This strategy will be followed and live actions will be organized for such relevant occasions, trying to get a higher visibility and involvement of the community.

Other interactive actions include the organization of contests. A big Science Slam Video Contest is intended by the end of the current year. Ideally, applicants will send a short Science Slam video explaining a SUNRISE S&T concept and addressing the general public. The videos will be voted for via social networks, with the best entries being uploaded to the website. The creators of the

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videos will be awarded the opportunity to attend the SUNRISE Symposium (incl. travel costs), where they will receive their prize, perform their Science Slam entry and have the opportunity to disseminate their research/projects, etc.

Finally, a further opportunity for interaction will be choosing a new logo and name for the new initiative resulting from joining SUNRISE and ENERGY-X. A contest could be organized to let stakeholders vote some possibilities. This can be a good opportunity to already create awareness of the new action and bring together the two communities. This is to be discussed with the ENERGY-X preparatory action.

- **Outreach activities:** SUNRISE partners are encouraged to introduce the SUNRISE project in participatory events where they already contribute, *i.e.* open days, Pint of Science festival, European Researchers' Night, etc. In addition, SUNRISE has participated with two stands in two big events like the Big Challenge Science Festival (Norway) and EUSEW (Brussels), see Annex 1 for more information on past outreach activities. The next planned event is the Maker Faire in Barcelona, next October where the action will hold a stand as a selected project to be presented in the areas of circular economy and resilience and creativity. More related events will be identified in the following months and online campaigns will also be created and followed to reach a large public.

4.5. Education objectives and audiences

The major goal of a future education plan will be to identify the training needs for the new technologies to be developed within a big research and innovation project and develop a myriad of actions to cover them. This identification will be run together with specialized academic institutions (*i.e.* LERU – League European Research Universities and EUA – European Universities Association are SUNRISE supporters) and industrial associations (EMIRI is a partner). The educational activities will be mainly aimed at the following audiences:

- Primary and secondary school students
- Undergraduate students
- PhD students
- Researchers and technicians in academy and industry

4.6. Education tools and actions

While the education plan is conceived as a future action, within the CSA some of the included activities have an educational character. Analysis of these activities and their future application will constitute the basis of the future plan:

- **Young researchers travel grant contest:** providing opportunities to young researchers to attend dissemination events to present their results and interact with the scientific community is of great value for their formation. Therefore, calls for travel grants should be included in the Education plan. Moreover, in a future large-scale project, *specialized workshops* should be organized devoted to new technological advances and other subjects such as innovation, economic and life cycle analysis, gender issues, legal concepts, etc. Special *workshops for young students* should also be taken into account and even *summer stages* for undergraduates and high school students could be a good option.

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- **Leaflets and infographics:** these are also relevant materials that can contribute to educational aims. A circular economy and a facts&figures infographics will be developed during the CSA. Extension to broader subjects and also more technical leaflets could also be part of the Education plan.

- **Science Slam Video Contest:** interactive actions with the participation of students might encourage their engagement in the project and knowledge sharing. Therefore, these kind of actions are also of interest.

- **Visits to schools and Universities:** our Empa partner, Artur Braun, has visited several Universities to present the SUNRISE project (University of Mersin, University of Taurus, University of Pretoria). While, other partners have an active role participating in educational events by their universities, for instance, Huub de Groot, from Leiden University, participated in the WND Noordwijkerhout, Conference 'energy in transition' for high school teachers (December 2018) and Lunchlezing lectures during lunch for master students Chemistry and LST (March 2019). This strategy of having project's representatives participating in schools and universities' events to present the large-scale initiative goals and participation opportunities might have a large impact towards the engagement of young students and is an option to be explored in the future plan.

5. PARTNER'S RESPONSIBILITIES

All SUNRISE partners contribute to public engagement and disseminate and communicate SUNRISE action.

Partners must use the project's logo and EU emblem in all their dissemination and communication activities.

ICIQ is the WP Leader of the WP3. Dissemination, Communication and Education. Therefore, ICIQ will be in charge of:

- Managing and updating the webpage (except intranet, M2i) and social networks both with self and external contents in coordination with the management team;
- Releasing the newsletters (every 3-4 months);
- Provide partners with appropriate dissemination, communication and outreach materials;
- Support the management team and other partners in the preparation of SUNRISE events;
- Be in charge of videos' production and main documents design;
- Generating, collecting, evaluating and archiving press releases, dissemination and communication activities developed during SUNRISE;
- WP deliverables preparation;
- Informing consortium members about important aspects related with this WP;
- Organise and moderate online activities, *e.g.* contests, chats, etc.

In addition, each partner will have his/her own responsibilities:

- To inform and send the WP3 leaders the SUNRISE press releases managed by their institution (at least one);
- To keep a fluent communication with the management and dissemination, communication and education team and, whenever possible, provide information and graphic material (such as pictures, blog posts, etc.) of any dissemination or communication activities developed within the framework of the project to be released through the website and promoted via the social media channels.

6. ACTIVITIES EVALUATION (short-term)

To evaluate the impact of the dissemination and communication activities developed during the project different indicators will be collected. Based on the analysis of the activities carried in the first months and the objectives and actions described, the updated list of KPIs to be checked by the end of the action is as follows:

Table 2. Updated KPIs

Tool	KPI	Target at the end of CSA
Website	Number website visits	>15,000 ^a
Newsletter	Number subscribers	>500 ^b
Social/Professional networks	Number of followers	>2,500 ^a
	Interactions (shares, likes)	>10,000 ^b
Videos & podcasts	Number views (YouTube channel)	>2,500 ^c
CSA Events (symposium, industry workshops and meetings, outreach activities, etc.)	Attendees SUNRISE central events	>350 (in total) ^d
	Attendees national Stakeholder workshops	>200 (in total) ^c
	Attendees outreach actions	>200 (in total) ^d
Letters/statements of support	Number	>250 ^b
Press releases & clippings in media	Number	>50 ^b

^a Decreased number in accordance with current trends; ^b Increased number in accordance with current trends; ^c New KPI; ^d Reformulated KPI.

In addition, qualitative values (such as number of visited pages per visit to the website, most viewed posts, etc.) and other values such as the number of interviews with consortium members in radio/TV, etc. will also be monitored through the action.

7. LONG-TERM OBJECTIVES

Additional objectives will need to be taken into account for planning a long-term dissemination, communication and education strategy within a large-scale initiative. Nowadays the model to be followed to develop the future initiative is still uncertain and future strategies will need to be agreed with the ENERGY-X project, nevertheless some of the possible long-term objectives include:

- ***Consolidate a visual identity and develop website and social media tools:*** bring the two communities together, trying to drag reached followers and supporters in the continuation initiative and minimising costs and efforts reusing all possible tools. In addition, an Instagram account could also be opened as this is a useful branding tool to increase project's visibility among the lay public and the youth in particular. It could be interesting to share pictures of experiments and demonstrators.
- ***Include a deeper stratification by working communities:*** set a functional organization that allows providing appropriate materials and contents by working groups (*i.e.* special news for material development, biohybrid development, etc.). Especially important for the organization of different specialized workshops and/or central events with satellite symposiums and for reaching industrial stakeholders with potential interest in the new developed technologies.
- ***Keep increasing policy makers and citizens' involvement:*** continue with the dissemination work at large scale, including projects results presentation to European and national policy makers and their involvement, for instance in the definition of new policies and standardization to deploy the new technologies, etc. Keep developing communication tools to reach society at large (*i.e.* simultaneous live events, interviews in local media, videos, development of gaming and informative smartphone applications) and increase citizen's involvement by the introduction of social sciences studies, such as standardized surveys to compare technologies awareness and inclination to use the new technologies by EU countries, etc.
- ***Strengthen collaboration with decision-makers and other international initiatives:*** identify different campaigns from the European Commission, associations, and NGOs, in order to cooperate with them, with special emphasis in attracting the lay public. Establish cooperation and symbiosis strategies with other European and international actions, *i.e.* Mission Innovation (where 4 of the 8 challenges are directly relevant to the SUNRISE initiative), European Energy Research Alliance (EERA) and its Joint Programmes, International Solar Energy Society – ISES, Joint Center for Artificial Photosynthesis – JCAP, etc., to participate in global initiatives and establish joint calls.
- ***Create an open access portal:*** establish tools to efficiently manage the generation of new publications and their sharing to quickly provide the latest updates to the involved community, including possible development of an App.
- ***Create the project's own outreach resources:*** develop outreach materials and demonstrators, in addition to organize projects actions in cooperation with interested actors, *i.e.* itinerant expositions in science museums.
- ***Develop the project's educational plan:*** establish connections with relevant stakeholders, *i.e.* universities and industrial associations, to create *ad-hoc* training materials and a system of calls for young researchers and workshops organization.

8. LONG-TERM DISSEMINATION, COMMUNICATION AND EDUCATION PLAN

Most of the tools and actions of the current action can be kept at a minimum cost after the end of the CSA: website, social media tools, dissemination at related events, etc. Depending on the following projects format and funding, different options are possible. The basic backbone of the long-term dissemination, communication and education plan is shown in the following table:

Target group	Actions and Tools	Aim
Research community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website & social media - Dissemination at related events & specialized initiative workshops - Travel & workshops grants and education materials - Participation in research networks - Newsletters & leaflets - Press releases & videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website & social media - Create awareness of new results and advances - Increase critical mass and avoid duplication of efforts - Establish contact with other research projects; enhance synergies and collaborations - Create an Open Access Portal
Industry sector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website & social media - Dissemination at related events & specialized initiative workshops - Publications in industry journals - Newsletters and leaflets - Travel & workshops grants and education materials - Press releases & videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create awareness of the disruptive potential of the project's technologies - Identification and investigation of novel business opportunities and partners. - Identification of standardization needs for implementation of solar fuels - Create an Open Access Portal
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website & social media - Dissemination at Energy-related European and national events - Newsletters and leaflets - Outreach activities and surveys - Press releases & videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Create awareness of the project and its potential impact - Secure governmental support and coordinated investment in solar-to-fuel and solar-to-chemicals technologies - Favorable policies and required standardization - Create an Open Access Portal
Multiple advocacy groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website & social media - Newsletters and leaflets - Outreach activities and surveys - Gaming and information phone apps - Press releases & videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase public engagement and social contribution - Involve different disciplines and attract new users - Increase awareness of the role of EU funding in supporting innovative research on carbon-neutral technologies - Create an Open Access Portal

9. ALIGNMENT WITH THE DMP

The dissemination, communication and education actions will be in line with the data strategy and procedures described in the D3.4 Data Management Plan (DMP). Specifically, these are the main following points that will be taken into account:

- Data storage and security: the main storage tool will be the Project website, hosted in internal servers (ICIQ), including the main internal information exchange tool, the intranet PLAZA managed by M2i. All the dissemination and communication material will be available (during and after the project) on the SUNRISE website and ZENODO
- Data access, sharing and reuse: all data related to personal information, mainly person contact names from partners and supporters and e-mail addresses, will be kept under the password protected intranet site. Personal data collected will be kept under a minimum, following GDPR rules, including user consent and information access, especially relevant for subscription to newsletters, using a marketing platform (Mailchimp)
- Data preservation and archiving: the SUNRISE public website will be maintained for at least 3 years after the project completion. Dissemination and communication materials will also be uploaded to public repositories, i.e. ZENODO, for preservation but also for sharing and reuse.

ANNEX 1

Analysis of the SUNRISE Dissemination and Communication Actions, M6

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1. THE SUNRISE COMMUNITY

One of the main goals of the CSA project is to build a growing supporting community. Table 1 shows the total number of subscribers/followers that the action has reached in the first 5 months (up to 31 July).

Table 1. Global community

	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019
Platform	Number subscribers/ Followers*	Number subscribers/ Followers*	Number subscribers/ Followers*	Number subscribers/ Followers*
Twitter	144	220	293	316
Research Gate	49	59	65	79
Facebook Page	5	213	232	301
LinkedIn Page	17	35	90	117
YouTube Channel	N/A	3	19	27
Newsletter	342	470	585	610
TOTAL	477	1000	1284	1450

*Cumulative data at the end of each month.

The data analysis starts in April 2019 once all the social media (except the You Tube channel) have been created. The Twitter account (December 2018) and the Research Gate page (February 2019) were already working before the CSA project started and counted with some followers, while Facebook and LinkedIn pages were created once the action started in March 2019. The number of followers of the social media tools have heavily increased in the first months of the action. The supporting community is expected to keep growing in the following months, although at a slower pace.

A SUNRISE YouTube channel has also been added to the communication tools. This channel was not included in the first proposal plan, it was created having a pivotal role to easily share the CSA's videos and podcasts among the SUNRISE community.

Regarding the newsletter subscribers, the first newsletters were sent to keep a close communication with the different stakeholders that have sent supporting letters to back the initiative. In April 2019, the CSA had received official endorsement of around 150 institutions worldwide. Currently, the action has received 222 letters of support. Therefore, the supporting community, including stakeholders from academia, industry, and society counts already with 242 organisations, an overview can be found in the following table:

Table 2. Overview of the SUNRISE working community

	Academia	Industry	National Network	European Network	Funding body	Miscellanea/ NGO/ Ministry	Total	#Countries
Partners	15	3	-	2	-	-	20	13
Supporters	125	68	11	6	3	9	222	25
TOTAL	139	72	11	8	3	9	242	25

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The number of the newsletter subscribers has been growing in the first months of the CSA, including new supporter contacts, registered attendees at the “SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop” held in Brussels (June 2019) and spontaneous subscriptions through the webpage. Different newsletter updates have been sent, depending on the audience (if only partners, supporters and External Advisory Board (EAB) or broader audience) and the message (see more information on point 3.4).

2. EVALUATION DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND ACTIONS

2.1. List of events where the SUNRISE project has been (or will be) presented

SUNRISE partners have been very engaged and active introducing the initiative in the numerous conferences, workshops and meetings where they have participated. In addition, an initial presentation meeting was held last year, November 2018, to present the initiative to the already built community, before knowing the evaluation results. Another big community event was the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop that joined a big representation of supporters and followers and that took place in connection with the EU Sustainable Energy Week 2019. The other consortium meetings held during the CSA also tried to involve interested stakeholders, offering streamline and open sessions to supporters. See the table below with the different events:

Table 3. Events where SUNRISE has been/will be introduced:

Event	Partners involved & dissemination material used	Estimated No. attendees
15 November 2018, Brussels. <u>SUNRISE Meeting</u>	Consortium members and supporters / slides	90
30 January 2019, Leiden, <u>Symposium 'Incredible Innovation' organised by student association 'De Leidse Biologen Club'</u>	Huub de Groot (Leiden University), invited speaker, lecture: Kunstmatige fotosynthese en biosolar cells	- ^a
26 January 2019– 1 February, Oslo. <u>CoE NordAqua – Nordic Bioeconomy Program Meeting</u>	Eva-Mari Aro (University of Turku) / slides	- ^a
6 March 2019: <u>Lunchlezing, theme: 'Bioenergy'; lecture during lunch for master students Chemistry and LST</u>	Huub de Groot, invited speaker / slides	- ^a
21-22 March 2019, Brussels, <u>SUNRISE Kick-off meeting</u>	Consortium members + PRD session online	22 partner representatives + ~40 supporters online
25-27 March 2019, Cambridge. <u>Artificial Photosynthesis Faraday Discussion & Mission Innovation action plan meeting</u>	Leif Hammarström (Uppsala University), James Durrant & Ernest Pastor-Hernandez (Imperial College), Víctor A. de la Peña (IMDEA Energy) / poster & leaflets	- ^a
25 March 2019, Brussels. Sunrise Preparatory Action Day.	Huub de Groot (Leiden University), Nicola Armaroli (CNR), Hervé Bercegol (CEA), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens) / project slides and explanation SUNRISE for the commission representatives,	- ^a

28-29 March 2019, Cambridge, UK <u>Solar Fuels Network Meeting</u>	James Durrant (Imperial College)	- ^a
16 April 2019, Lahti. <u>BioFuture 2025, Academy of Finland</u>	Eva-Mari Aro & Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides	- ^a
22-26 April 2019, Phoenix, Arizona. <u>MRS Spring Meeting 2019</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides for three different presentations	~150 in the Symposia (around 4,000 overall)
9 May 2019, Bologna. <u>EERA Workshop: R&D pathways and opportunities in Fuel cells, Hydrogen and Bioenergy</u>	Nicola Armaroli (CNR) / slides	- ^a
13-14 May 2019, Móstoles. <u>FOTOFUEL Workshop: Current challenges in solar fuels production</u>	Victor A. de la Peña (Organiser, IMDEA Energy), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens), Carolina Gimbert (ICIQ) / Poster, slides, leaflets	~ 150
13-15 May, Saclay. <u>Meeting of the GDR solar fuels</u>	Vincent Artero (CEA) / slides	- ^a
13-17 May 2019, Rome. <u>Energy Materials Nanotechnology conference, EMN Rome 2019</u>	Joanna Kargul (University of Warsaw) / slides	~ 80
15-16 May 2019, Bologna. <u>SUNRISE Consortium Meeting.</u>	Consortium partners and invited Italian supporters	30 partner representatives + ~15 supporters in the final session
17 May 2019, Helsinki. <u>Meeting of Finnish Research Foundations.</u>	Eva-Mari Aro (University of Turku) / slides	- ^a
22-24 May 2019, Turku. <u>Nordic Photosynthesis Congress NPC14</u>	Eva-Mari Aro & Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides	- ^a
27-31 May 2019, Nice. <u>E-MRS Spring Meeting, sponsoring a poster within the symposium: Materials for Energy – Latest advances in solar fuels</u>	Antoni Llobet (ICIQ), Artur Braun (Empa), Mariam Barawi (IMDEA Energy), Carlota Bozal-Ginesta (Imperial College, SUNRISE Young Researchers Travel Grantee) / slides, poster + sponsor poster prize	~200 for lectures & poster session symposium A (2700 full conference)
27 May 2019, Donostia-San Sebastian. Spanish Royal Society of Chemistry Biennial Meeting 2019- <u>Light Symposium: Light controlled materials and processes: from medicine to artificial photosynthesis</u>	Victor A. de la Peña (Co-organiser Symposium, IMDEA Energy), James Durrant (Imperial College)/ slides	- ^a
29 May 2019, Vancouver. <u>Clean Energy Ministerial meeting, CEM10</u>	Ann Magnuson (Uppsala University) / leaflets	- ^a
5 June 2019, Warsaw. <u>SUNRISE Poland Stakeholder Workshop</u>	Organisers: Joanna Kargul & Renata Solarska (University of Warsaw), SUNRISE Speakers: Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) + Hervé Bercegol (CEA) / video, slides, leaflets	~60
13 June 2019, Mersin University. <u>International Conference “Solar / Fuel Cells: Energy Systems”</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides, roll-up	- ^a

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12-14 June 2019, Bucharest. <u>9th edition of EuroNanoForum</u>	Joanna Kargul (University of Warsaw), Laurent Baraton (ENGIE) / video, slides	- ^a
13 June 2019, Mersin University. <u>International Conference “Solar / Fuel Cells: Energy Systems”</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides, roll-up	- ^a
17-18 June 2019, Brussels. <u>SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop</u>	Consortium partners and interested stakeholders	~170
17 June 2019, Brussels, <u>Global Alliance for Powerfuels panel</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) as panel speaker	~70
20 June 2019, Brussels. EUSEW Session: <u>ENERGY STORAGE TO BOOST EU DECARBONISATION AND COMPETITIVENESS</u>	Huub de Groot (Leiden University)	~600
23-27 June 2019, Aachen. <u>17th International Conference on Carbon Dioxide Utilization – ICCDU 2019</u>	Hélène Lepaumier (ENGIE) / poster (winner poster prize), leaflets	320 (full conference)
24-26 June 2019, Lipari. <u>UK-IT Joint Meeting on Photochemistry 2019</u>	James Durrant (Imperial College), Tony Vlcek (J. Heyrovsky Institute of Physical Chemistry-UCL)	- ^a
26-30 June 2019, Portoroz-Portorose. <u>6th European Conference on Environmental Applications of Advanced Oxidation Processes</u>	Fernando Fresno (IMDEA Energy) / slides	- ^a
1-3 July 2019, Brussels, <u>ENERGY-X “Research need” Workshop</u>	Huub de Groot (Leiden University), Vincent Artero (CEA), Ann Magnuson (Uppsala University), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens), Eva-Maria Aro (University of Turku), Julio Lloret-Fillol (ICIQ), Carina Faber (UCL) / leading/participate in the different discussion panels	~180
5-12 July 2019, Paris. <u>47th IUPAC World Chemistry Congress & 50th General Assembly</u>	Vincent Artero (co-organiser symposium 2.3, CEA) / leaflets	- ^a
8-10 July 2019, Marseille. <u>Quantum BioInorganic Chemistry Conference (QBIC-V)</u>	Andrey I. Konovalov (Leiden University, SUNRISE Young Researcher Travel Grantee) / slides	- ^a
21-26 July 2019. Newry. <u>2019 Photosynthesis Gordon Research Conference</u>	Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides, leaflets	- ^a
30 July 2019, University of Pretoria. <u>Talk SUNRISE Project</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides, roll-up, leaflets	- ^a
31 July – 02 August 2019, Pilanesberg National Park, South Africa <u>Energy Storage and Industry 4.0: Challenges and Prospects (ENSTIN 2019)</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides, roll-up, leaflets	- ^a
4-9 August 2019, Durban. <u>70th Annual Meeting of the International Society of Electrochemistry</u>	Artur Braun (Empa), Renata Solarska (University Warsaw) / slides, roll-up, leaflets	- ^b
18-23 August 2019, Aachen. <u>14th European Congress on Catalysis, EuropaCat 2019</u>	Frédéric Chandezon (CEA), Hervé Bercegol (CEA), Maximilian Fleischer (Siemens AG) / leaflets	- ^b

25-30 August 2019, Barcelona. <u>World Congress on Light and Life</u>	Eva-Mari Aro (University of Turku) / slides	- ^b
27-30 August 2019, Donostia-San Sebastian. <u>Photo- and ElectroCatalysis at the Atomic Scale</u>	Franziska Hegner (ICIQ, Young Researchers Travel Grantee) / slides	- ^b
28 August 2019, Galway. <u>Potential of Biohybrid Solar Reactors for CO₂ Valorisation Workshop</u>	Joanna Kargul (University of Warsaw) / slides	- ^b
3 September 2019, Warsaw. <u>62nd Annual Scientific Meeting of the Polish Chemical Society</u>	Joanna Kargul (University of Warsaw) & Dorota Rutkowska-Żbik (ENERGY-X representative from Haber Institute in Cracow) / video, slides	- ^b
9-13 September 2019, Venice. <u>1st International e-conversion Conference</u>	Joanna Kargul (University of Warsaw) / slides	- ^b
19 September 2019, Brussels. <u>Workshop on CCU Innovation Fund and other EU Funding Opportunities, by CO₂ Value Europe</u>	Anita Schneider (EERA) / slides	- ^b
21 September 2019, Leiden. <u>“De nacht van de ontdekkingen”</u> ; Public Science night in Leiden	Huub de Groot, invited speaker, talk “Artificiële fotosynthese” / slides	- ^b
22-23 September 2019, Tarragona. <u>4th EuCheMS Conference on Green and Sustainable Chemistry</u>	Antoni Llobet & Julio Lloret & Elisabet Romero (ICIQ, local advisory board) / slides, roll-up	- ^b
26 September 2019, Brussels. <u>ENERGY-X Research Roadmap Launch event</u>	Carina Faber (UCL) / Participation in the discussion panel	- ^b
27 September 2019, Dübendorf. <u>SUNRISE Switzerland Stakeholder Workshop</u>	Organisers: Artur Braun & Rita Toth (Empa), together with the Swiss supporters: Pierdomenico Biasi (Casale) and Sophia Haussener (EPFL). Presentation SUNRISE by Frédéric Chandezon (CEA) / video, slides, roll-up	- ^b
30 September -1 October 2019, Brussels. <u>EABA Algae Based Biofuels Workshop</u>	Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides, leaflets	- ^b
2-3 October 2019, Móstoles. <u>Aportando Valor al CO₂ (Increasing value of CO₂)</u>	Victor A. de la Peña (IMDEA Energy), Laura López (ICIQ) / poster, slides, leaflets	- ^b
2-4 October 2019, Rome. <u>Biophysics of Photosynthesis</u>	Eva-Mari Aro & Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides	- ^b
8 October 2019 – Paris – <u>ANCRES (French national energy research alliance) workshop on the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X initiatives for French stakeholders</u>	Organizers : Hervé Bercegol (CEA), Frédéric Chandezon (CEA), Simon Perraud (CEA) /slides, leaflets	
9-11 October 2019, Brussels. <u>SUNRISE Consortium meeting & Meeting with Mission Innovation</u>	Consortium partners + representatives Energy-X + EAB + Mission Innovation (IC6)	- ^b

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25 October 2019, Leiden University Reedijksymposium 2019	Huub de Groot (Leiden University), invited speaker/slides	- ^b
6 November 2019, Eindhoven. Symposium “Solar to Products”	Huub de Groot (Leiden University/ slides & demonstrator	- ^b
9 December 2019, Turku, Finnish SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop	Eva-Mari Aro & Yagut Allahverdiyeva-Rinne (University of Turku) / slides	- ^b
10-13 December, Arusha. <u>10th Conferenced of the African Materials Research Society</u>	Artur Braun (Empa) / slides, roll-up	- ^b

^a Data not available, ^b Data collected until 31 July 2019.

Although most of the events where the initiative has been presented are scientific conferences targeting academic and industrial researchers, it is worth highlighting that policy actors have also been present in some of the events. For instance, a governance session with European Member States and European associations and foundations representatives was included in the SUNRISE stakeholder workshop. In addition, local policy members representatives have also been invited to the different national stakeholder workshops (Poland, Switzerland). The project also had a dedicated session in the 9th EuroNanoforum, while participation of the SUNRISE coordinator in a session within the EU Sustainable Energy Week was an important highlight to reach this audience.

During the month of April, the SUNRISE initiative organized a “Young researchers travel grant” contest among partners and supporters to cover the travel costs (up to 400€) of three young researchers (PhD students and up to 4 years postdoctoral researchers) to attend a scientific event to disseminate their research. Candidates should present an accepted abstract to the call in a research theme related to one of the three SUNRISE approaches. The three awarded researchers have delivered oral talks (see events in the table above) and used social media or blog posts to announce the talk, mentioning the SUNRISE action in the acknowledgements.

In collaboration with E-MRS, a SUNRISE supporter, the initiative sponsored a poster prize in the Symposium A “*Latest Advances in Solar Fuels*”, at the European Materials Research Society (E-MRS) Spring meeting 2019 held in Nice, France. The winner poster was entitled “Ni-modified β -FeOOH(Cl) nanorod for water oxidation toward solar-driven CO₂ reduction system combined with Mn-complex catalyst”. Authors: Tomiko M. Suzuki, Takeo Arai, Shunsuke Sato, Keita Sekizawa, *Takeshi Morikawa Affiliations: Toyota Central R&D Labs., Inc.

Finally, in addition to the presentation in conferences and other events, the SUNRISE initiative has also appeared in relevant scientific publications. A description of the project was included in the “News Flash” section in the last edition of the European Photochemistry Association Newsletter, June 2019 (invitation through Leif Hammarström, Uppsala University). SUNRISE has also been mentioned in other articles in Nature (replicated in Scientific American), Science Magazine and Chemistry World, together with the other preparative actions and related projects. Finally, a publication about the six preparative actions and a news about the SUNRISE Stakeholder Workshop also appeared in the Digital Single Market portal from the EC.

2.2. Smartphone app

One of the objectives of the dissemination plan is to develop a new smartphone app to share scientific publications. At the moment a demo version is available (<http://events.tickaroo.com/projectsunrise/>). During the CSA period this version will be tested within consortium partners to share their latest publications, the

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feedback of the first users will be key to develop a future version open to the full SUNRISE community and a public one in a future advanced development. This system is thought to be a new tool to support open access strategies. The first demo was already presented at the SUNRISE Stand during the Energy Week (see point 3.8).

2.3. SUNRISE Password Protected Site

The project's website is the main tool for dissemination and communication purposes and a better description can be found in point 3.2. Especially relevant for the dissemination purposes is the password-protected site: <https://sunriseaction.com/priority-research-directions-prd-vision/> which contains the PRDs and other working documents. Only the initiative's partners and official supporters are given the password to access it (sent through informative newsletters). This site has become an important tool to keep a strong interaction with the growing SUNRISE community, as it is one of the most visited pages.

2.4. Poster and slides

A poster titled 'SUNRISE: Solar energy for a circular economy' has been created to showcase the project in different events. It is available in the intranet PLAZA of the project's website together with standard slides for presentations.

In addition, the SUNRISE poster won the 'Best Poster Award' at the 17th International Conference on Carbon Dioxide Utilization (ICCDU), which took place on June 23 – 27, 2019, in Aachen, Germany.

3. EVALUATION COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND ACTIONS

3.1. Project logo and visual identity

A logotype was designed to advertise the project at the time of the proposal preparation. The SUNRISE logo is the visual element that represents the project and promotes instant public recognition. The logo was designed with a simple and dynamic look representing a sun rising over the fields, directly related with the claim of the project: solar energy for a circular economy.

The SUNRISE logo together with the EU emblem and the sentence "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 816336" must be included by all partners in all the communication and outreach documents and events.

Regarding the SUNRISE logo, at the beginning of the project a Twitter contest was launched offering the possibility to vote between the existing logo and two more options. This action aimed to increase involvement of followers and supporters in the action and attract attention to the Twitter account. The majority of participants voted to keep the current option and SUNRISE mugs were sent to participants that voted in the second leg of the poll.

Figure 1. Logo twitter poll

3.2. SUNRISE Website

The SUNRISE website is accessible at: www.sunriseaction.eu and www.sunriseaction.com. The website is the main online dissemination and communication tool of the project. It contains information on the project, the consortium and its members, projects achievements, related events, audiovisual resources and current activities. This information is addressed to all sorts of audiences, from scientists and industrial researchers to the general public.

The website has been designed following a responsive web design (RWD) to enable optimum visualization independently of the size of the screen (PC, tablet and mobile) or web browser one is viewing with. It has been and will be updated frequently as required by ICIQ.

The platform has been created to serve as a project content management system on two levels: (1) external communication and dissemination of the project objectives and results, and (2) internal Communication Platform within the consortium. The public section displays the following sections:

- **Home:** basic title and description of the project, highlights of the latest news, events and videos, contact information, access to the other web sections and to the project social networks (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn and ResearchGate).
- **About us:** information about the CSA, the project's vision, FAQ about the initiative, and the list of all partner institutions taking part in the project, linking to their short descriptions. Every partner is briefly described in terms of research quality, groups participating in SUNRISE and people responsible for the project.
- **Newsroom:** pieces of news about the project, interviews with experts, SUNRISE meetings, related events, opportunities, and useful resources, such as publications, presentations and videos. It will also include infographics in the coming months.
- **Blog:** brief updates about SUNRISE communication and outreach activities, and contents written by external authors.
- **Support us:** general contact form to become a supporter and a banner with all the current supporters' logos.
- **Media:** collection of the press releases, media appearances and coverage of SUNRISE news published in general and specialized newspapers and magazines, interviews (radio and TV), videos, etc.

In the website, there is a direct link to the intranet site PLAZA: <https://sunriseaction.com/intranet/> and is managed by M2i. It can only be accessed by the project's consortium members and has been created to exchange documents, files and other confidential information between the project partners. The intranet is

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the main tool for storage and exchange of documents between partners, such as:

- Complete contact list including names and e-mail addresses of all the participants
- Templates
- Minutes of the meetings
- Progress reports
- Deliverables

More details about the web design can be found in the public project’s deliverable “3.2. Project website, App and social media tools”. Although the action counted with a public website since September 2018, evaluation of the website traffic and audience has not been done until May 2019, once the new web has been designed and Google Analytics tools properly displayed.

Table 4. Website traffic analysis (Google Analytics)

Website statistics	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019
Sessions	1137	1785	1536
Users	618	985	963
Page views	6508	8308	9684
Pages/session	5,72	4,65	6,3
Average Session Duration (min:sec)	0:05:25	0:04:52	0:05:14
Location overview			
Country #1	Spain	Belgium	United States
Country #2	Italy	France	Spain
Country #3	France	United States	France
Top 3 pages			
Page #1	Home, 1599 views	Home, 1600 views	Home, 1000 views
Page #2	PRDs, 430 views	PRDs, 656 views	Consortium, 460 views
Page #3	Events, 349 views	Events, 552 views	Past events, 427 views

The information tracked by the analytics tool shows that the page had 4458 visits between May and July 2019 as counted by the number of sessions, which gives the estimate of the number of times visitors opened the website. The number of users for the same period is 2566 showing that some of the visitors have opened the website more than once in this period of time, and even more importantly, the page visitors spend long times at their visits generally seeing more than one page, giving therefore large page views numbers.

It is also interesting to see that beyond the home page, the most visited pages include the password-protected PRDs page where the working documents can be accessed by the projects core group partners, supporters and EAB. Indicating a big interaction with project main stakeholders, who are contributing to shape the project’s goals. The events page showing events taking place with partners and supporters participation is

also of interest for the SUNRISE community, having this into account the events page has recently been redesigned to allow easier navigation.

Interestingly, location overviews show a big interest from United States visitors, highlighting the international relevance that the project is acquiring. This fact might be important when setting new social media campaigns, as some can be directed towards American public.

3.3. Social Networks

Social networks are used to promote the content of the project's webpage, related projects and relevant news concerning artificial photosynthesis. Each social media has been further analysed through its own analytic tools (Tables 5 to 9):

Table 5. Twitter Account Analysis (Twitter Analytics, <https://twitter.com/sunriseaction>)

	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019	Total
Num. of tweets	50	96	144	38	259*
Impressions	40200	77600	135000	79700	-
Engagement rate	1,7%	0,9%	1,5%	1,7%	-
Replies & likes	154	336	615	265	1370
Retweets	50	110	175	89	424
Link clicks	152	251	471	206	1080
Total Interactions (Replies&likes + retweets + link clicks)	356	697	1261	560	2874

*The total number of tweets since December 2018, when the account was opened, is 488 at 31 July.

Table 6. Research Gate Analysis (Research Gate stats, <https://www.researchgate.net/project/SUNRISE-Solar-Energy-for-a-Circular-Economy-EU-H2020-CSA-Ref-816336>)

	Feb-Apr. 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019	Total
Num. of updates	16	5	11	3	49
Recommendations	21	20	31	30	102
Reads	454	76	174	370	1101
Total Interactions (Recommendations + reads)	471	96	205	400	1303

Table 7. Facebook Page Analysis (Facebook Insights, <https://www.facebook.com/sunriseaction>)

	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019	Total
Num. of updates	2	23	21	18	64
Impressions*	76	46032	120718	129837	-
Likes	1	49	103	58	211
Shares	0	5	12	12	29
Total Interactions (likes + shares)	1	54	115	70	240

*Cumulative data (sum of all impressions of the page) at the end of each month

Table 8. LinkedIn Page Analysis (LinkedIn Analytics, <https://www.linkedin.com/company/sunriseaction>)

	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019	Total
Num. of publications	13	12	16	11	52
Impressions	978	2090	3130	1946	-
Engagement rate	5,8%	6,8%	8,3%	6,4%	-
Clicks	43	62	158	62	325
Reactions	14	60	67	57	198
Total Interactions (Clicks + reactions)	57	122	225	119	523

Table 9. You Tube Channel Analysis (YouTube analytics, https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWBoKlQrVNn_cJsTSwGz0pA)

	April 2019	May 2019	June 2019	July 2019	Total
Num. uploaded videos & podcasts	N/A	2	1	3	6
Impressions	N/A	45	267	618	-
Views	N/A	107	886	291	1284

The analysis shows that social media are being active and generating the desired interactions with the SUNRISE community. The Twitter account, being the first social media to be active, has turned the main social media tool of the action with the major number of followers and interactions. Actually, these tools, together with the password-protected site in the website and newsletters (see following point) have proved to be the real interaction points with the SUNRISE community, substituting the initial idea of a discussion forum in the website.

Another interesting point is that posts with most engagement both on Twitter and Facebook are those related to SUNRISE events and news, rather than the external news that are shared on a regular basis, meaning that SUNRISE's audience is interested in the project's updates and followers are committed to the initiative.

D3.1.

3.4. Newsletters

To establish a good communication with the action supporters, regular newsletters have been sent to the organization's contacts. A marketing management tool, such as Mailerlite or Mailchimp, has been used to centralize and manage the communication to a large number of contacts. In this way, the SUNRISE community members have been invited to participate in the SUNRISE presentation meeting on November 2018 and the SUNRISE Stakeholder Meeting on June 2019. The registration link, agenda and any logistic information has been shared through this channel. Furthermore, the supporters have been invited to contribute to the definition of the PRDs and Vision through informative newsletters, providing them with a password to have access to the working documents.

To further facilitate quick access to all SUNRISE stakeholders and keep growing the ecosystem around the project, a public newsletter has also been prepared to inform subscribers about the latest news and advances of the project. The first public newsletter was submitted on July 2, 2019 to 585 subscribers and it obtained 34,70 % opens (at 31 July). Mailchimp is currently used as our marketing platform, allowing recipients to unsubscribe at their will.

3.5. Videos and podcasts

The project has produced a general video to socialize the initiative's objective. The video was released in June and has more than 740 views in the YouTube channel. A direct link is also available in the project website (resources section) and has been pinned in the other social media tools, having 1200 views in the LinkedIn page (31 July).

Other videos include:

- Facebook live interview with the SUNRISE Deputy Coordinator, Hervé Bercegol (CEA) in occasion of the International Day of Light (1600 views on Facebook Page, 31 views on YouTube channel);
- Promotional video SUNRISE Stakeholders Workshop (132 views YouTube channel, 94 views Facebook page, 326 views Twitter)

In addition, SUNRISE partners have been invited to radio interviews, podcasts of the last interviews to Victor de la Peña (IMDEA, in Spanish) and Nicola Armaroli (CNR, in Italian) are also available in the [YouTube channel](#).

The consortium members will be encouraged to produce audiovisual material to be freely distributed through the webpage and the institutional YouTube channels of the partners. Other external videos related to the artificial photosynthesis will be posted on the project's website to attract the lay public's attention to the topic.

3.6. Templates and branding elements

Templates for word documents, letters, slides, etc., containing layout and styles used to create standardized documents have been designed to ensure a unified corporate image. The templates are available in the intranet PLAZA of the project's website.

In addition, a factsheet, a leaflet and roll-ups containing the project's logo, title, consortium members, social media channels and a call to action are already available to be used in consortium meetings, workshops, industrial fairs, congresses, etc. as branding materials.

3.7. Press releases and media presence

Three official press releases have been launched by the SUNRISE initiative:

Press release announcing the action (1 February 2019)

Press release about the SUNRISE Stakeholders Workshop (21 June 2019)

Joint press release with ENERGY-X about plans to merge the two initiatives (27 August 2019)

Press releases have been published in the partner's websites and some translated into 10 different languages: English, French, German, Dutch, Italian, Czech, Polish, Finnish, Swedish and Spanish. A non-exhaustive search shows more than 50 press releases replications, links or SUNRISE mentions in the partners' websites, related institutions websites and external general media and specialized magazines and online portals, for instance: La Province, Energy Post, Lab Worldwide, Energeek, Enviweb, Rinnovabili, among others. Moreover, press releases have also contributed to get partners interviews, in online publications: Uppsala University website (Swedish), Chemistry World (English), BioBasedPress (English and Dutch), Industriemedien (German publication available for Austrian subscribers, English version in the blog section of the webpage) and InnovaSpain (Spanish); and also on radio shows: RAC1 (Catalan), Radio Internacional (Spanish) and RadioCittadelCapo (Italian).

3.8. Outreach activities

Three main outreach activities have been carried out during the first months of the project:

- Twitter chat

A Twitter online discussion was organized on occasion of the World Environment Day on June 5, 2019. The main objective of the chat was to discuss about the role of renewable energies in reducing air pollution. The one-hour online discussion started had four subject experts from various backgrounds related to the sustainable energy field (**Kate Black**, Communications Director at **Metabolic**; **2. Julio Lloret**, Group Leader at the Institute of Chemical Research of Catalonia (**ICIQ**); **3. Marcella Bonchio**, Full Professor of Advanced Organic Chemistry and Coordinator of the Nano & Molecular Catalysis Laboratory (NMC LAB), at the **University of Padova**; **4. Philippe Schild**, Senior Expert of the Renewable Energy Unit of the Directorate General (DG) of Research & Innovation at the **European Commission**). Besides the four participants, other users took part in the conversation by sharing their views on the different tweeted questions. A wrap-up of the session can be found on the website blog (<https://sunriseaction.com/blog/>).

- SUNRISE stand at the Big Challenge Science Festival

On June 16-19, researchers from SUNRISE partner NTNU held a stand at the Big Challenge Science Festival in Trondheim (Norway). Visitors, mostly children and teenagers, but also researchers and administrative staff from NTNU, could learn about artificial photosynthesis and the SUNRISE project. Researchers from the Koch group received visitors in an interactive stand where they could watch the official video, play with an online App showing how photosynthesis and artificial photosynthesis works and watch live experiments. One of the experiments showed how a toy car can run with hydrogen generated from a fuel cells and solar panels, while another one was performed by researchers coming from the Kargul group in U. Warsaw showing how solar cells made with algae pigments can harvest solar energy. In total, the stand counted with around 120 visitors.

D3.1.

- SUNRISE stand at the EU Sustainable Energy Week

On June 20, SUNRISE participated in the EU Sustainable Energy Week with a stand in the Networking Village. Visitors, around 25, mostly professionals from the industrial and policy sectors, could learn about the SUNRISE project through the vision of the SUNRISE official video and other branding materials such as the official leaflet. In addition, visitors could see and give their opinions about the SUNRISE App demo.

Be a change maker & Join our community!

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